

4th Medicinal and Biological Chemistry Ireland conference

Report by: Gerd K Wagner*

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University Belfast

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Organisation: held under the auspices of the Medicinal & Biological Chemistry Division of the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland and the European Federation for Medicinal Chemistry & Chemical Biology (EFMC)

Event Sponsors

Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section; Institute of Chemistry of Ireland; Almac; Clinigen Ltd; ThermoFisher Scientific; SK Biotek; GPE Scientific Ltd; Trinity College Dublin; The Thomas J Moran Graduate School, Queen's University Belfast

Summary

From 15-16 July 2025, the School of Pharmacy at Queen's University Belfast hosted the 4th Medicinal and Biological Chemistry Ireland conference, under the auspices of the Medicinal & Biological Chemistry Division of the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland, and the European Federation for Medicinal Chemistry & Chemical Biology. Following on from successful previous editions at Trinity College Dublin (2016), Dublin City University (2018), and NUI Galway (2022), the meeting exceeded expectations, with 110 participants, 44 submitted abstracts, and strong buy-in from industry.

The scientific programme covered a broad range of topics across chemical biology, medicinal chemistry

and drug discovery, from small molecules to protein therapeutics, antibody-drug conjugates, and chemical probes for in vivo real-time optical imaging. The roster of 11 invited speakers included internationally leading scientists as well as rising stars, from these shores and beyond, and from both academia and industry.

As a new element, and in addition to the scientific programme, on its second day the conference also featured a Lunchtime Careers Fair, aimed mainly at Early Career Researchers (ECRs). During the careers fair, participants could attend showcase presentations by ThermoFisher, SK Biotek, GPE Scientific, and EU OpenScreen, as well as a careers "speed dating" event with industry delegates. The speed dating session gave

ECRs an opportunity to meet “up close” with industry professionals and ask those questions about a career in industry they had always wanted to ask, but maybe never had the chance. The careers fair was extremely well received by participants and may well become a permanent feature of future editions of this conference.

The conference schedule was rounded off by a social gathering over a pizza and a pint on Tuesday night at the Botanic Inn, including a mini trad session (another conference feature to be retained?)

And, as the final act, the outgoing chair of the Medicinal and Biological Chemistry Division, Isabel Rozas, was recognised with flowers for her immense contribution to the Division, and her tireless efforts to promote the cause of medicinal and biological chemistry in Ireland!

Attendees

With 110 registered delegates, attendance exceeded expectations, with well over half of all participants either PhD students (59) or postdoctoral scientists (11). Efforts had been made specifically to make the conference attractive to ECRs, e.g., through introduction of the careers fair and the opportunity for co-chairing scientific sessions, and these efforts appear to have paid off.

While the majority of participants (78%) hailed, unsurprisingly, from academic institutions or industrial organisations across the island of Ireland, there was also a significant contingent (12%) from Great Britain, as well as individual delegates from as far afield as Hungary and Chile. Women were slightly underrepresented, with 46% of all delegates identifying as female.

Table 1. Scientific programme.

Session 1: MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY (15 July)		
11:10	Don Weaver	University of Toronto
12:00	Trinidad Velasco-Torrijos	Maynooth University
12:30	Joe Byrne	UCD
Session 2: CHEMICAL BIOLOGY & PROTEIN THERAPEUTICS		
14:00	Nicholas Mitchell	University of Nottingham
14:50	Eddie Myers	University of Galway
15:20	Graham Cotton	Almac Discovery
Session 3: CHEMICAL BIOLOGY & DRUG DISCOVERY (16 July)		
9:00	Mark Bradley	QMUL
9:50	Joanna MCGouran	TCD
10:20	Daniel O'Donovan	AstraZeneca
Session 4: DRUG DISCOVERY IN ACADEMIA (16 July)		
14:15	Angela Russell	University of Oxford
15:05	Lorraine Martin	QUB

Support from industry was strong, not only in the form of sponsorship, but also through the active participation of 12 representatives from a diverse range of industrial organisations large and small. Notably, many of the industrial delegates gave up their time to participate in the careers fair and “careers speed dating” event, for ECRs.

Target audience: ECRs (postgraduates, postdocs), industrialists, academics

Programme

The scientific programme included a series of 11 invited lectures (Table 1, Figure 1), 4 flash presentations by ECRs selected from the submitted abstracts (Figure 2), and a poster session (Figure 3). The invited lectures were grouped thematically into sessions on Medicinal Chemistry, Chemical Biology & Protein Therapeutics, Chemical Biology & Drug Discovery, and Drug Discovery in Academia, although the boundaries between these themes remained necessarily fluid. ECRs were given the opportunity to co-chair sessions, an opportunity that was enthusiastically taken up by Celia Paramio and Luke Brennan (ICI Young Chemists' Network) and Catherine Webley (QUB).

Figure 1. The invited speakers (from left to right): Dr Graham Cotton (Almac), Dr Joanna MCGouran (TCD), Prof Angela Russell (University of Oxford), Dr Trinidad Velasco-Torrijos (Maynooth University), Prof Mark Bradley (Queen Mary University of London), Prof Lorraine Martin (Queen's University Belfast), Dr Daniel O'Donovan (AstraZeneca), Prof Don Weaver (University of Toronto), Dr Nicholas Mitchell (University of Nottingham), Dr Joe Byrne (UCD) and Dr Eddie Myers (University of Galway)

Figure 2. Left: the flash presenters (from left to right) Guru Vigknes (University of Galway), Francis M. Barnieh (Bradford University), Periklis Karamanis (University College Dublin), and Timea Baló (Eötvös Loránd University). Right: flowers for Isabel!

Prizes

The quality of the submitted abstracts was extremely high, and while sponsorship had been secured for no less than four sponsored poster prizes, the judges had a hard time selecting the winners. In the end, they settled on the following contributions by ECRs: Celine Erkey (PhD student, UCD) “Posttranslational Modifications of Human Interferon Gamma for Improved Therapeutics” – Almac Discovery Poster Prize; Nikhil Bajpayee (PhD student, QUB) “A Chemical Toolbox for Targeting β -Strand Mediated Protein-Protein Interactions” – Almac Discovery Poster Prize; Lorcan Rooney (PhD student, QUB) “A Photocleavable Boronic Acid-Based Nanomaterial for the Study of Sialic Acid-Siglec Activation” – ICI Poster Prize; and Riona Devereux (postdoc, University of Oxford) “Identification of the lipid-protein interactome: A chemo-proteomic approach to understand cardiometabolic dysfunction” – ThermoFisher Poster Prize (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Left: a snapshot from the poster session in the Thomas J Moran Graduate School. Right: the winners of the poster prizes (from left to right) – Celine Erkey (UCD); Lorcan Rooney (QUB); and Nikhil Bajpayee (QUB). Not in the picture: Riona Devereux (University of Oxford)

Figure 4. Impressions from the social evening and trad session

Feedback

While many enthusiastic comments about the conference were received informally from delegates, formal feedback was sought specifically about the careers fair, as this was a new addition to the conference schedule. ECRs were sent a questionnaire with 9 questions relating to the careers fair shortly after the end of the conference. 16 responses (23%) were received. All respondents found the careers fair “very useful” (71%) or “somewhat useful” (29%), and just under 40% stated that the careers fair had influenced their decision to attend the conference in the first place. The company showcase presentations were described as “very useful” by 64% of respondents (“somewhat useful”: 21%), and the speed dating session by 52% (“somewhat useful”: 43%). Aspects that were identified for improvement concerned mainly the time allocated to the careers fair as well as logistics. There were many constructive suggestions that should be taken on board if, as seems desirable, the careers fair becomes a permanent feature of future editions of this meeting.

“the careers fair should definitely continue, as many PhD researchers are considering transitioning into industry. Having the opportunity to receive first-hand insights from professionals currently working in industry is very valuable.”

“More info about internship [...] opportunities”

“more time for the speed dating”

“I really appreciate that it was in small groups. It is easier to speak with the industrials, and others ask questions that I did not think about.”

“I particularly liked the speed dating session, because it allowed us to engage directly with the speakers and ask questions in a more relaxed environment.”

Acknowledgements

We wish to reiterate our gratitude to the following organisations for financial support of the conference: The Royal Society of Chemistry, Republic of Ireland Local Section; the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland; Almac; Clinigen Ltd; ThermoFisher Scientific; SK Biotek; GPE Scientific Ltd; and Trinity College Dublin. Without their support, the conference would not have been possible.

We are grateful to the following industry delegates, who gave up their time for the “careers speed dating” event with our early career researchers: Lena Demetre, Daniel O’Donovan, Graham Cotton, Shane Rountree, Victoria Mora, Michael Gurry, Conor Fennell, Tadhg Kelly, and Orla Patton. The careers fair and poster session took place in the Thomas J Moran Graduate School at Queen’s, who made their beautiful space available for the conference on a no-cost basis – thank you!

And last not least, I would also like to personally thank my research group, staff in the School of Pharmacy school office, and the events team, catering staff and porters at Queen’s University Belfast for their respective contributions to the smooth running of the conference.

The Division of Medicinal and Biological Chemistry

The aim of the Division of Medicinal and Biological Chemistry of the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland is to promote the fields of Medicinal and Biological Chemistry among academic and industry researchers in Ireland by encouraging collaborations within the island and to enhance the innovative potential of the Irish-based research groups. The Division is affiliated with the European Federation of Medicinal Chemistry and Chemical Biology. More information about the Division can be found at <https://www.chemistryireland.org/ici-division-of-medicinal-biological-chemistry/>

References

A blow-by-blow account from both days of the conference, including additional pictures, can be found on my personal LinkedIn profile: <http://www.linkedin.com/in/gerd-wagner-6807936/>

Previous Events in this Series

- 3rd Medicinal and Biological Chemistry Ireland conference, NUI Galway (2022)
- 2nd Medicinal and Biological Chemistry Ireland conference, Dublin City University (2018)
- 1st Medicinal and Biological Chemistry Ireland conference, Trinity College Dublin (2016)